

The 3-dimensional structure of the prototypical young system T Tauri

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Abstract

In this contribution I present my latest analysis of the orbits in the famous triple system T Tauri. I discuss what we can deduce about the 3D structure of the system and the long-standing question whether T Tau S is in front or in the back of T Tau N. I also describe how a circumbinary disk around T Tau Sa/Sb can explain the brightness fluctuations of T Tau Sb, because its orbital motion moved it behind the denser parts of the disk in 2016. In the coming years, the motion of T Tau Sb will allow us to probe the near side of the circumbinary disk.

1 Introduction

T Tauri is the best-observed member of the class of stars named after it, but astronomers are still debating what exactly is happening in the system. Its irregular photometric variability has been puzzling since its discovery. We know it is a triple system, it contains the close binary T Tau Sa/Sb and the third component T Tau N about 0.6 arcsec to the North (Fig. 1). All three stars have circumstellar disks and outflows.

Figure 1: The T Tauri system imaged with the adaptive optics instrument SPHERE at the Very Large Telescope on December 9, 2014, displayed with a logarithmic scale (from Köhler *et al.*, 2016)

2 The Orbits

The relative positions of the stars in the triple system were measured over about 25 years by many different observers (see Schaefer *et al.*, 2020, and references therein). We used a Monte Carlo Markov chain (MCMC) sampler (Foreman-Mackey *et al.*, 2013) to study the possible orbits in the system, based on the available astrometric observations. To determine the orientation along the line of sight, we rely on radial velocity measurements: Hartmann *et al.* (1986) give a radial velocity of 19.1 ± 1.2 km/s for T Tau N, while Duchêne *et al.* (2005) measured radial velocities of 22.0 ± 1.3 km/s for T Tau Sa and 21.1 ± 1.3 km/s for T Tau Sb. Therefore, at the time of the measurements in 2003, T Tau Sb was moving towards us relative to T Tau Sa, while both together were moving away from us relative to T Tau N (according to our orbit model, the direction of motion has not changed since the observation of Hartmann *et al.* 1986).

Figure 2 shows the binary T Tau S, seen from two directions to illustrate its 3D-structure. Also displayed is the inner part of the circumbinary disk proposed by Köhler & Kubiak (2020), and the extinction caused by it. From 2002 to 2014, T Tau Sb was in the north-west section of its orbit (PA $\sim 280^\circ \dots 340^\circ$), where it was less obscured by the dense parts of the circumbinary disk.

Figure 3 contains two views of the entire T Tau N/Sa/Sb triple. Because of the limited orbital coverage, the outer orbit (T Tau N around T Tau S) is highly uncertain. The orbit depicted in the figure is the best fit for the observations, with a period of 2730 years. However, the MCMC sampler found possible solutions with periods between ~ 1300 and 33 000 years.

3 Is T Tau S in front of T Tau N?

Beck *et al.* (2020) presented a 3-dimensional model of the T Tauri system. They explain the brightest region of [S II] emission in the system as collision of two outflows from T Tau N and S, which would place T Tau N ~ 620 AU behind the T Tau S binary. Our orbit solution predicts that T Tau N is actually in front of T Tau S (see Fig. 3). However, astrometric measurements contain no information about the po-

Figure 2: The orbits of T Tau Sa and Sb around their center of mass, and the inner part of the circumbinary disk.
Top panel: the system seen from the positive declination axis, with the observers on Earth located at the bottom. In this view, the left edge of the disk is in front.
Bottom panel: the system as we see it from Earth. Here, the right edge of the disk is in front.
 The dashed line is the line of nodes. The dashed-dotted line marks T Tau Sb’s periastron. The red cross and arrow indicate its position on 1. Jan. 2020 and the direction of motion.
 A movie showing a 360° rotation of the system can be found at <http://www.rainerkoehler.com/TTau>.

sition along the line of sight, there are always two solutions that are mirrored at the plane of the sky. To resolve this ambiguity, we rely on the radial velocity measurements by Hartmann *et al.* (1986) and Duchêne *et al.* (2005). Given the uncertainties, we cannot exclude that the orbit is actually

Figure 3: All three orbits in the T Tau system, and the circumbinary disk around T Tau S. Like in Fig. 2, the top panel shows the view from the positive declination axis, and the bottom panel as seen from Earth. The orbit of the center of T Tau S is shown in green, with T Tau N in the center of the orbit. T Tau S is drawn in green at its position on 1. Jan. 2020. Its direction of motion is indicated by the green arrow. The orbits of T Tau Sa and Sb around their center of mass are shown in blue, and the circumbinary disk in orange.

oriented the other way, i.e. the way suggested by Beck *et al.* (2020). However, our best orbit predicts a separation along the line of sight of less than 200 AU, about one third of the distance in the geometrical model of Beck *et al.* (2020). We computed the separation between T Tau N and S along the line of sight on 1. January 2020 for one million orbit solutions sampled by the MCMC algorithm. The result is shown in Fig. 4. While there are orbit solutions where the distance is larger than 600 au, the majority of orbits predicts much smaller distances. Therefore, the orientation suggested by Beck *et al.* (2020) is unlikely, although we cannot fully exclude it.

Figure 4: The distribution of distances between T Tau N and S along the line of sight. This is the result of one million orbits sampled by the MCMC algorithm.

4 Conclusions and Outlook

The orbit of T Tau Sa/Sb is well constrained by the available observations. Within the uncertainties, we find the same orbital elements as [Schaefer *et al.* \(2020\)](#). On the other hand, the orbit of the wide pair T Tau N/S is still uncertain. The best-fitting orbit model has a period of 2730 years, but the confidence interval extends from 1300 to 33 000 years. Considering that we collected astrometric data for only 21 years, this uncertainty is hardly surprising.

The photometric variations of T Tau Sb can be explained by its orbital motion and a circumbinary disk inclined by $\sim 60^\circ$ at a position angle of $\sim 30^\circ$ ([Köhler & Kubiak, 2020](#)). If this suggestion is true, then T Tau Sb should have emerged from the disk by now and become brighter again. On the other hand, the suggested circumbinary disk cannot explain the extinction towards T Tau Sa, unless it is very thick (extended above its midplane). In this case, T Tau Sb would probably not come out of the near side of the disk at all, and remain faint until 2029. In 2023 T Tau Sb will reach the pericenter of its orbit, which is near the apocenter of the orbit of T Tau Sa. New observations of the system by then would help to shed light on the structure of the circumbinary material.

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